

**“FROM DEGREE TO CAREER: A DEEP DIVE EXPLORATION INTO JOB
PROSPECT AND EMPLOYABILITY RATE OF COMPUTER ENGINEERS IN
THE CONTEMPORARY WORLD”**

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the range of job opportunities and employability rate of computer engineering graduates and undergraduates as they move from their degree to develop their successful careers within a technology-driven industry. The study uses a quantitative approach to collect and analyze numerical data to understand and develop conclusions regarding a certain event or group. The survey is then distributed among 15 students and 5 graduates across the various satellite campuses of Bulacan State University. The researchers discovered that many respondents plan to pursue careers in computer engineering, while others intend to follow different paths such as teaching or becoming a Firmware Engineer. The researchers also found that the computer engineering field has a high employability rate, as graduates were employed in jobs directly related to their field of study. Job opportunities for both undergraduates and graduates include roles such as Software Developer/Engineer, Hardware Engineer, Systems Analyst, Network Engineer, Quality Assurance Engineer, and Data Analyst/Game Developer. The study focuses on assessing the career pathways, job opportunities, and employability of computer engineering students and graduates. It examines the variables affecting their transition from education to employment including the programming languages and technical skills valued by employers, and the job position preferences of the students. It is recommended in the study the improvement in curriculum, teaching methods, resources, support systems, and parental involvement can enhance programming education and student outcomes in the computer engineering field.

Keywords: Deep Dive, Career, Employability, Engineering Fields

INTRODUCTION

Every day, the advancement of electronic computer technology improves our quality of life. It brings with it an increasing number of issues, increasing the need for computer engineers now more than ever. According to an article in Field Engineer, computer engineering is important for the advancement of technology that supports our daily lives. However, what exactly is the job of a computer engineer, and what do computer engineers do? A computer engineer is a professional who designs, develops, and maintains computer networks and systems using knowledge from electrical engineering and computer science.

The last few decades have seen a significant evolution in computer systems. Computer engineers are responsible for designing, testing, and enhancing these systems, which is the reason for their existence. A career in this field can lead to high-paying positions with some of the most well-known businesses in the world, such as Google, Amazon, and Apple. Despite a slower-than-average growth rate of 5%, computer engineers earned a healthy median annual salary of \$128,170 (P7, 218, 662.57) in 2021. Furthermore, given the widespread adoption of computers in various technological applications, the need for computer engineers is expected to persist in the future. Given the rapid growth of the technology industry, they may be concerned about job stability and the probability of employment. Some of them may be concerned about the industry's diversity and inclusion, as well as how it will affect their job possibilities and experiences. Since there is a strong need for computer engineers, there is also a lot of competition. They may be concerned about standing out from their peers and gaining promising employment possibilities.

As computer engineering students, we are also constantly thinking about what field or career we can pursue once we graduate. Many computer engineers (both graduate and undergraduate students) still want to work in the software sector, possibly as software engineers, but many lack confidence in their abilities. There are also CPE students who are currently studying and contemplating the field they want to pursue in the future.

The researchers seek to solve this problem by researching the possible jobs and the employment rate of computer engineers, with a title of **“From Degree to Career: A Deep Dive Exploration into Job Prospect and Employability Rate of Computer Engineers in the Contemporary World.”**

Research Objectives

- To identify the potential job opportunities for computer engineering students and graduates.
- To assess the employment rate for computer engineering graduates and students in jobs directly related to their field of study.
- To find the key factors affect computer engineering graduates as they move from finishing their degrees to starting successful careers.
- To explore which programming languages and technical capabilities are companies seeking when employing computer engineering students or graduates.
- To identify the preferences of engineering students with regards to various job positions within their field?

Significance of the Study

This study will be able to contribute research-based data for the incoming and present computer engineering students and alumni, as well as students and future researchers.

To the Computer Engineering Student(s). CpE students will have a better understanding of what they want to do after graduation because of the information provided by this research.

To the Computer Engineers (Graduates). The results of this study will assist the CPE graduates in selecting a career path that complements their bachelor's degree.

To the Incoming College student(s). Through this study, prospective college students who have not yet decided which program they want to enroll in will be able to choose

this program because of the career opportunities available under the program of computer engineering.

To the Researchers. They may be able to use this study to provide them with information on the jobs and careers they may pursue.

To the Future Researchers. The study's findings benefit future researchers; this may serve as one of the foundations for new learning.

Review Related Literature

Related Theories

The Maturation Career Theory. Jeffrey Sonnenfeld and John P. Kotter (1980). According to Sonnenfeld and Kotter, the career theory has evolved throughout the last century. This theory explains occupational variables such as work type and wages, as well as psychological variables like job satisfaction and job-related stress. It has a long history spanning over a century and contains at least four distinct categories or traditions of research. In relation to this theory, individuals advance through distinct stages as they develop in their roles, eventually leading to increased degrees of responsibility and influence within the business. This theory can help everyone by tracking individuals' professional progression from entry-level to senior leadership roles, investigating the factors that influence their success, and discovering common patterns or stages of development.

Social Cognitive Theory. Albert Bandura (1986). Bandura claimed that learning takes place in a social setting, with a dynamic and reciprocal interaction between the individual, environment, and behavior. This idea describes how each of us learns, develops, and adapts to our social environments. It emphasizes the complex interaction of cognitive, social, and environmental aspects in determining human behavior and provides insights into effective ways for encouraging learning, behavior modification, and personal growth.

Human Capital Theory. Becker Gray (1976). According to Gray, human capital analysis is motivated in part by a desire to evaluate proposals for improving labor quality through education, training, medical services, and child care. The essential concepts of this theory include investment in education and training, productivity and earnings, lifetime earnings, transferability, and economic growth. Higher levels of human capital are related to higher earnings and more work opportunities, whereas skills and knowledge gained via education and training can be used in a variety of vocations, sectors, and occupations. This philosophy emphasizes the significance of education and training in achieving personal achievement and economic wealth.

Related Literature

What Is Computer Engineering? Career Guide + FAQ (Coursera, 2024), computer engineering is a combination of computer science and electrical engineering. This field of research combines numerous disciplines to create software and hardware systems. Although computer science and computer engineering are closely related, there are a few significant differences. Both need critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and technical knowledge. However, computer scientists are more concerned in theorizing and developing methods for using software to address real-world issues. They must be able to use programming languages like Python and Java. Computer engineers work with computers, from software to hardware, including operating systems and robotics. Computer engineers collaborate with other engineers and programmers to design and test computer systems' functionality.

Computer Engineering (2024), computer engineers are influencing industries by creating computer-based solutions for specialized purposes. They operate in computing, aerospace, telecommunications, power generation, manufacturing, defense, and electronics, developing cutting-edge technology ranging from microelectronic chips to powerful and efficient telecommunications systems. Consumer electronics (CD and DVD players, televisions, stereos, microwaves, gaming devices), as well as advanced microprocessors, peripheral equipment, portable, desktop, and client/server computing systems, and communications devices (cellular phones, pagers, personal digital assistants), are all examples of applications.

It also encompasses distributed computing environments (local and wide area networks, wireless networks, internets, and intranets), as well as embedded computer systems. A wide range of complicated technological systems, such as electricity generation and distribution systems, as well as modern processing.

Computer Engineering (CCECC, 2024), in today's world of computer and technology computer engineers are essential in today's technological and computer-driven environment. It is necessary for creating new and improved things in a variety of fields. Computer Engineering is the science and technology that involves creating, constructing, connecting, and maintaining the hardware and software components of modern computer systems and computer-controlled machinery. It was thought for a long time that computer engineering was a combination of computer science (CS) and electrical engineering (EE). In choosing computer engineering as your preferred course, you will begin your coursework with basic scientific and math classes including physics, calculus, and general chemistry.

Learn more about computer engineering in the Philippines! (2022), according

to an article of Online Education (2019), the article stated that computer engineering program is challenging and students can rest assured that they are not required to prepare for and pass a Board Licensure Exam to enter the workforce. Upon obtaining their degree, they can immediately enter the job market after earning their degree.

The article emphasizes the accessibility of job opportunities for computer engineering graduates and the absence of licensure requirements in their career path.

5 Promising Computer Engineering Careers (Dimas SEO, 2022) by selecting relevant courses, you could focus on a particular aspect of computer engineering. In essence, computer engineering is the process of designing and developing the hardware and software needed to make computers function properly. In today's digital world, computer engineering jobs are growing in popularity and demand, offering great chances and good pay.

Are Computer Engineers High in Demand? (ComputerCareersOrg, 2024), a report by the US News & World Report in 2009 also said that computer engineers have one of the best careers, along with systems analysts and network architects. Looking ahead, the employment opportunities for computer engineers will continue to expand gradually in the future, making this a popular career choice.

Related Studies

According to Aguila, De Castro, Dotong, & Laguador (2016) the percentage dropped to 81.82% for the 2014 batch and then to 66.7% for the 2015 batch. Nine out of ten computer engineering graduates who were employed acquired regular or permanent positions within six months after graduating. Salaries, benefits, and possibilities for career progression were identified as common factors for employees choosing to stay in their current positions. 16 out of 23, indicated that the program at National University-Manila was relevant to their first employment. This discovery highlights the level of competition among graduates in the job market, which is affected by the curriculum they studied (Ahmad et al., 2012). Aguila's research found that the key factor keeping computer engineering graduates in their positions is salary and perks, with professional challenges being the second most important reason. This supports the results of the present research.

According to Chavez (2017), the perceived efficiency of engineering courses in conveying Aristotle's philosophical, continuous research process is one of its main advantages. The curriculum intends to strengthen students' ability to communicate the language of mathematics, engineering, and science with other fields, as well as to work in multidisciplinary teams. It promotes the ability to reason about mathematical and scientific knowledge, often known as engineering science or the reductionist model.

According to a study conducted by De Castro, Prenda, Dolot, Laguador, and Donong (2016), employers prefer employees that take the initiative and are motivated to complete the job in an acceptable amount of time. This is where quality measures come into play, providing a check and balance on the performance's outputs and outcomes. A cheerful attitude gets the job done and inspires others to do the same, rather than concentrating on the inevitable problems that arise in any workplace. A passionate employee fosters a great work atmosphere and serves as a role model for others. It is something that managers and coworkers value the most, and it also makes coming to work more pleasant and enjoyable each day.

According to researchers Chavez, De Castro, Camello, and Laguador (2016), despite the fact that program objectives are designed to match the stated needs of industry, engineering graduates may lack the competencies required for modern practice. This observed gap between education and practice alludes to a series of underlying reasons that contribute to the competency challenge in engineering education.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 2.2. Factor Influencing Career Choices (Ahmad 2016)

Utilizing the diagram, the researchers are exploring the job prospects and employability rate of computer engineers in the contemporary world. Theoretically, this model gives the researchers a framework for the possible factors that can affect the careers and job opportunities of every computer engineer/student. The financial outcome, interest in the subject, ease of subject, and future opportunities are several factors that influence choices regarding a profession. Other external or internal variables may have influenced students' decisions, either directly or indirectly.

METHODS

Research Design

The study uses quantitative data to organize approaches used to collect and analyze numerical data to understand and develop conclusions regarding a certain event or group. And in this research, the researcher aims to know the range of job opportunities and employability rate of computer engineers as they pursue their career paths.

This quantitative research is a descriptive research centering on the exploration into job prospects and employability rate of computer engineers in the contemporary world of the computer engineering students and graduates. According to QuestionPro (2020), it is a quantitative research method that attempts to collect quantifiable information for statistical analysis of the population sample. In addition, the researchers are to learn about and analyze the future career pathways of computer engineering students, both undergraduate and graduate.

Specifically, with quantitative data to be gathered from the survey questionnaire, the researchers will be able to determine the range of job opportunities and employability rate of computer engineers once they pursued their career in this field.

Participants

A purposive sampling strategy was applied to collect and select a total of 200 respondents from the population of Bulacan State University-Main Campus and various satellite campuses, which served as the study's location. These include selected computer engineering graduates as well as university undergraduate students. The 200 respondents were divided into two groups: 150 computer engineering undergraduate students (75%) and 50 computer engineering graduates (25%) respectively.

Research Instruments

The objective of this research is to look into the variety of job options and employability rates for computer engineering graduates as they progress from their degree to successful careers in a technology-driven industry. This study's specific goal is to

identify answers to the stated problem statement. The survey questionnaires, created using Google Forms, offer students an easy-to-use platform to share their experiences and insights. The results of the research are expected to provide insight into the anticipated occupations and career prospects rates of computer engineers when they graduate.

The survey forms will be validated by experts in computer engineering education, such as professors from Bulacan State University's Department of Computer Engineering or other qualified professionals. Their thorough assessment will guarantee that the survey form is understandable, appropriate, and consistent with the purpose of the research objectives, so increasing its efficiency in collecting accurate information.

Procedures

The researchers used Google Forms in order to create survey questionnaires that provide students with an easy way for them to express their experiences and views. After creating the questionnaire, the researchers proceeded on to the process of having it assessed by an expert. When the expert approved it, the researchers sent the survey questionnaires to the selected respondents. The study's findings are expected to shed light on the projected vocations and career prospects of computer engineers after graduation.

The researcher used different survey response scales. The first one is Dichotomous Scales, for the questions that only have two response options which are "yes" or "no" and "graduate" or "undergraduate". The researchers also Satisfactory Scale for the last two parts of the survey form which number 5 is the "Most Satisfied" and 1 as the "Most Dissatisfied". Lastly, Categorical Scale for the respondents to select one option from a list of predefined categories.

Data Analysis

To proceed with the research, the researchers gathered and collected data. The statistical approaches listed below were utilized to evaluate and analyze the data collected for this investigation.

Percentage and Mean

The number of respondents participated for the data collection is determined by the frequency with which each response is provided. The percentage formula will determine the demographic makeup of the respondents.

Ethical Consideration

To ensure the confidentiality of the respondents, aliases and codes will be shown instead of their actual names. Also, the online form that submitted by the respondents does not include their names or private/sensitive information

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- **How to identify the potential job opportunities for computer engineering students and graduates.**

To begin the data collection process, we need to determine whether the respondents are graduates or undergraduates. For this study, we will be collecting the records of five graduates and fifteen undergraduates from various branches of Bulacan State University.

Based on the data gathered, IT companies, which include software and web development firms, as well as IT consultancies like Google and Microsoft, account for 65% of the survey respondents are the industries or companies most likely to hire computer engineering fresh graduates. Electronics manufacturing companies, which involve making electronic components and devices such as Intel and Samsung Electronics, account for 15%. Startups, which are new companies across various industries needing computer engineering for innovation and product development, account for 10%. Additionally, telecommunications firms specializing in telecom infrastructure and network equipment, like Cisco Systems, account for 10%. Lastly, the gaming and entertainment industries each account for 5%.

- **How to identify the employment rate for computer engineering graduates and students in jobs directly related to their field of study.**

Of the five graduates who provided information, 80% were employed in a position

directly related to computer engineering at the time of the survey, while 20% were unemployed and not actively looking for work.

- **How to find the key factors affect computer engineering graduates as they move from finishing their degrees to starting successful careers.**

To determine the employment rate for the computer engineering career path, we first collected data regarding the intentions of undergraduates and graduates in pursuing careers in this field. Based on the data collected, 80% of the respondents said they intended to pursue a career in computer engineering, while 20% said they had other plans to do so. The factors that might impact pursuing a career in computer engineering were determined by the survey questionnaire. Technical skill deficiencies, including those related to hardware design, software development, programming languages, and other relevant fields, were cited by 75% of respondents as important contributing causes. Meanwhile, location was identified as concern by 25% of respondents.

- **How to identify which programming languages and technical capabilities are companies seeking when employing computer engineering students or graduates.**

Table 4.1: How satisfied are you with your proficiency in the following programming languages and technical skills

Programming Languages (e.g., C++, Java, Python)

Satisfaction Level	Numerical Value	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	5	4	20%
Satisfied	4	6	30%
Neutral	3	7	35%
Dissatisfied	2	1	5%
Very dissatisfied	1	2	10%
Total		20	100%

Web Development (e.g., HTML/CSS, Javascript)

Satisfaction Level	Numerical Value	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	5	3	15%
Satisfied	4	3	15%
Neutral	3	9	45%
Dissatisfied	2	4	20%
Very	1	1	5%

dissatisfied			
Total			100%

Database Management (e.g., SQL, MongoDB)

Satisfaction Level	Numerical Value	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	5	4	20%
Satisfied	4	8	40%
Neutral	3	8	40%
Dissatisfied	2	0	0%
Very dissatisfied	1	0	0%
Total			100%

Operating Systems (e.g., Linux, Windows)

Satisfaction Level	Numerical Value	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	5	5	25%
Satisfied	4	4	20%
Neutral	3	5	25%
Dissatisfied	2	6	30%
Very dissatisfied	1	0	0%
Total			100%

Table 4.1 displays the number of respondents' answers categorized by their satisfaction levels, along with the calculated percentages for each level. We conducted a survey to assess the proficiency of undergraduate and graduate computer engineering students in various programming languages and technical skills. The results, shown above, highlight the proficiency levels of these students in the following areas: Programming Languages (e.g., C++, Java, Python), Web Development (e.g., HTML/CSS, JavaScript), and Database Management (e.g., SQL, MongoDB). These programming languages were rated at a neutral satisfaction level.

- **How to identify the preferences of engineering students with regards to various job positions within their field?**

In determining the job position preferences within the computer engineering field, the data gathered showed that 50% among the respondents wanted to become Software Developers/Engineers, 15% aimed to be System Analysts, 10% preferred to be Hardware Engineers, and 5% each chose Quality Assurance Engineer, Data Analyst, and Game Developer roles. Additionally, 5% of the respondents expressed interest in positions outside this field, such as Teacher and Firmware Engineer. Lastly, 5% were unsure about which career path to take.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The aim of this research is to investigate and evaluate the professional paths taken by computer engineering undergraduates and graduates at Bulacan State University's Main Campus and Meneses Campus. The study also intends to investigate the career paths and options accessible to computer engineers, including job titles, positions, specializations, and chances for career progression.

Based on the questionnaire provided that were prepared by the researchers and answers by the respondents: 15 computer engineering students, and 5 graduates, the survey was disseminated properly.

- The data analysis highlights key trends in the career paths of computer engineering students and graduates from Bulacan State University. Most graduates secure jobs in their profession, demonstrating their excellent employability in a variety of industries, such as IT, gaming, electronics manufacturing, and telecommunications. While many respondents intend to work in computer engineering, location and a lack of technical skills are mentioned as major barriers.
- Technical skills and programming language proficiency of undergraduate and graduate computer engineering students are important in this field. Table 4.1 presents respondents' satisfaction levels across various areas, including Programming Languages, Web Development, and Database Management. Overall, the results indicate a neutral satisfaction level among students regarding their proficiency in these skills.
- The job position preferences within the computer engineering field reveals a diverse range of career aspirations among respondents. The majority indicated interest in traditional positions such as hardware engineers and system analysts, then software developers and engineers. It was also evident that positions such as Game Developer, Data Analyst, and Quality Assurance Engineer were of interest. There were other individuals who were unsure about their career choice and some who were considering non-traditional jobs like firmware engineering and teaching.

Key Findings

- Despite the abundance of opportunities in the field of computer engineering, some students choose not to pursue careers in this domain due to lack of technical skills and geographical constraints.
- Students rated their proficiency level as neutral satisfaction in various areas of Programming Languages, Web Development, and Database Management.
- Internships or co-op experiences are widely recognized as valuable for securing employment after graduation. Most respondents expressed satisfaction with their significance, indicating their importance in developing real-world knowledge and industry experience.
- The respondents recognize the value of additional certifications or specialized training in enhancing their employability within the field of computer engineering. A considerable number expressed a great satisfaction with the role of these qualifications in improving their career opportunities.

Conclusion

1. What are the potential job opportunities for computer engineering students and graduates?
 - According to our survey responses, computer engineering students and graduates have a wide range of job opportunities available to them. Graduates are highly employable within their field, demonstrating excellent employability in industries such as IT, gaming, electronics manufacturing, and telecommunications.
2. What is the employment rate for computer engineering graduates and students in jobs directly related to their field of study?
 - From our survey of five graduates, one respondent is unemployed and not seeking employment, while the others are employed in positions directly related to computer engineering. This indicates that graduates with degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering are highly employable in positions relevant to their field.
3. What key factors affect computer engineering graduates as they move from finishing their degrees to starting successful careers?
 - While a high number of respondents intend to pursue careers in computer engineering,

some face obstacles such as location and a lack of technical skills.

4. Which programming languages and technical capabilities are companies seeking when employing computer engineering students or graduates?
 - To assess each respondent's technical proficiency and determine which programming languages are most appropriate for them, we provided a Likert scale. Students rated their proficiency levels with neutral satisfaction in various areas, including Programming Languages, Web Development, and Database Management.
5. What are the preferences of engineering students with regards to various job positions within their field?
 - Respondents' preferences for work positions in the field of computer engineering show a wide range of professional goals. The majority indicated interest in conventional positions like system analysts and hardware engineers, then software developers and engineers. Furthermore, there was interest in jobs such as quality assurance engineer, data analyst, and game developer. While some people were unclear of their employment choices, others thought about non-traditional positions like teaching and firmware engineering.

Recommendation

- **Teaching Methods**

- To foster an engaging and competitive learning environment, incorporate coding competitions, hackathons, and skill-based challenges or activities. These programs serve to not only enhance students' abilities but also provide a platform to assess their skills gaps effectively.

- **Career Guidance and Counseling**

- Provide career counseling services to assist students in making professional decisions and resolving doubts. These resources can help students discover their talents, match their competencies to market demands, and make educated choices about their future.
- Develop an active alumni network to provide mentorship and mentoring opportunities for current students. Alumni who have successfully transitioned into their careers can provide valuable insights and guidance to help students prepare for the job market.

- **Enhance Technical Skill Training**

- Institutions should focus on enhancing technical skills through advanced coursework, workshops, and hands-on projects, addressing skill gaps identified by respondents. Additionally, encouraging students to pursue valuable certifications and specialized training can significantly boost their employability.
- Invest in the latest software tools and educational resources to support programming education.
- **Support System**
 - Create a peer mentorship program so that students can help one another understand complex programming ideas. Additionally, offer students who require individualized help in particular programming domains one-on-one tutoring sessions. These programs provide a cooperative learning atmosphere and provide customized assistance to improve students' programming abilities all around.
- **Parental Involvement**
 - Organize parent education seminars and information sessions to help them understand the value of programming education and how they can support the education of their children. Encourage parents to participate in programming projects and events with faculty members to create chances for parental involvement. Through these programs, parents and teachers will be better able to work together to support students' programming endeavors.
- **Further Research:**
 - Encourage instructors to participate in research projects that investigate creative instructional strategies and educational technology for programming. Encourage collaborations with other educational establishments to share concepts and methods for enhancing students' programming abilities and jointly tackle shared issues. Through inter-institutional cooperation and research-driven innovation, these projects seek to improve the standard of programming education.

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